

THE IMPORTANCE OF USING CHARTS AND DIAGRAMS IN TEACHING PROBLEM SOLVING IN ELEMENTARY GRADES

Suleymanova Konul Qurbaneli

*Teacher of the Department of Natural
Sciences and their Teaching Technology
of the Sheki branch of ADPU*

Abstract

The tendency to develop one's abilities is natural for all people. This tendency should be inculcated from a young age and further developed at higher levels of education. It is possible to strengthen the self-confidence of students with the help of various tools and methods in training. Education has confirmed its importance as a guiding force of society and has always influenced its development. Organization of quality training is an indicator of the success of the educational process. A high level of education should fully meet the demands of society. In order to implement what we said, it is recommended to build training in primary classes on manipulative and animation exercises. From this point of view, it is very important to work out the system of necessary elements aimed at the realization of the expected results and the necessary elements for the version that includes the philosophy of mathematics teaching in general education schools in a more optimal way, to model the solution of the problem with visual aids, and to enliven it with the help of schemes and images. Step-by-step examination of the problem using diagrams and tables and illustrating these steps with the help of block diagrams helps to understand the problem visually. In the school teaching of mathematics, most of the students find it easier to solve examples and strive for it. Sometimes we encounter such a request from a student, an applicant, a student: "give me an example, I'll solve it!". Because solving the problem requires logical and mathematical thinking. Therefore, it is necessary to give priority to issues related to the use of schemes and tables in primary classes, in this way, to expand the scope of knowledge and worldview of students related to life and everyday life.

Keywords: problem, scheme, table, principle of visuality, visual learning, visual aids, whole-part model

Interpretation of generalizations on research materials: All the principles of didactics are used in mathematics lessons. And of these, it is the principle of visuality that plays a greater role in the mathematics education of primary classes. In the pedagogical literature, the content selection, criteria and requirements for the application of visual aids have been widely interpreted. Therefore, we will touch on the method of using visual-illustrative materials in relation to problem solving.

Visual training is based on certain experiences of students, where visual memory and judgment play an important role. But visual learning is not only based on the visual materials used.

The implementation of the principle of visualization in the lesson is based on two pillars:

- 1) Pupils' perception of vision and visual memory
- 2) Concepts that students have and gain

Visual aids are necessary for perception. Visual aids are not always necessary for visualization, including imagery. Because students can be given new knowledge based on their life experience and imagination. In accordance with the definition and specification of mathematics science, the visual aids used in mathematics classes clearly reflect the spatial forms and quantities of objects or events. This also

helps to reveal the mathematical essence of the taught subject, the problem to be solved. In mathematics lessons, especially in problem solving training, the principle of visuality has great didactic importance for the initial stage. Mathematics teaching in primary grades is based on live observations from the first lessons, where visual memory plays an important role. The next step after observation is comparison. At this time, students compare the objects they observe according to their quantitative characteristics. So, in order to understand the content of the textual problems and to distinguish the quantitative relationships between the quantities, pictures, diagrams and other illustrations are often used according to the content of the problem.

What is the role and importance of visualization applied at different stages of problem solving?

The use of visual aids in the process of problem solving makes it easier to "see" various mathematical dependencies between quantities, as well as to develop students' observation and comparison skills, speech, attention, and thinking. In classes I-II, object-visualization and graphic-visualization are widely used in the process of problem solving.

Visual aids used by the student as working material are called didactic material.

Classroom visual aids are visual aids that are displayed in front of all students. The advantage of these types of tools is that it is easy to move from concrete to abstract in the training process.

In general, in the process of problem solving, visualization plays the role of a "bridge" in expressing the problem text in mathematical language. Number sticks, geometric figures, numbers, action signs, attitude signs, various illustrations can be applied in problem solving training.

It is known that problem solving is often the main difficulty for the student. To overcome this difficulty, the teacher must have a well-thought-out work system.

Visual means used in the process of solving complex problems serve to express the life situation or events described in the problem in a more mathematical language.

When visualization is applied in problem solving training, the teacher's explanation and relevant words have a certain effect on the students' attention and imagination. That process can be described as follows:

It is necessary to gradually accustom the students to judge without applying visualization in solving problems related to the dependences between quantities and the properties of numbers. Of course, every judgment

made is based on the students' knowledge. Problem solving training is developmental in nature from concreteness to abstraction.

Every primary school teacher wants to give their students a deep knowledge of mathematics. He tries so

that his students are able to solve all types of problems provided for elementary classes. To achieve all this, the

teacher must have a deep understanding of the theory and methodological basis of mathematics education, including problem solving methods and the ways to teach them to students. The experience of mathematician-methodist scientists and advanced schools shows that fundamental teaching of solving complex problems in grades III-IV plays an important role in the mathematical preparation of students in higher grades. The use of different tools in problem solving training increases the activity and interest of students. Experience shows that visual description of quantitative relationships between quantities in the process of problem solving helps to determine the method of its solution. The most convenient tool in this work is the use of straight line pieces, rectangular strips.

The issue is the type of task that involves the known (condition) and the unknown (unknown) so that the student's task is to find the unknown based on the known. Step-by-step examination of the problem with the whole-part model and the description of these steps with the help of block diagrams helps to understand the problem visually. This method is a method that allows you to solve the problem visually by calculation instead of solving it formally by setting up an equation. Solving problems by building an equation has the purpose of comparison. It is not recommended that students solve these problems by constructing an equation. Because on the one hand, many problems are solved with the help of complex equations, which is not taught in primary classes. On the other hand, solving the problem with an equation, as we said above, is a formal method. In such cases, the connection between the steps of solving the equation and the condition of the problem is lost.

First, let's look at such an issue.

The issue. Two boxes contain 18 pencils. The number of pencils in the second box is 4 more than the number of pencils in the first box. How many pencils are in each box?

Until integers were taught, we used to solve these types of problems by choosing numbers and checking two conditions.

Condition 1 – the sum of two numbers is 18 (the number of pencils in two boxes),

2nd condition - the difference of two numbers is 4.

Two numbers with a sum of 18 and a difference of 4: $11+7=18$ is $11-7=4$.

However, as the numbers in the problem condition grow, it becomes difficult to solve these types of problems through sampling and verification.

Instead of the formal solution of the problem algebraically and with equations, solving it through real animation with models has a more positive effect on the development of the student's analytical thinking.

Students can develop problem-solving skills late by drawing a whole-part model. But the ability to convert information from text to graphics helps them solve more difficult problems later on. Therefore, it is necessary to create long-term habits by periodically returning to solving problems in this way. By constructing a full-part model of the problem, the explanation of the prob-

lems is explained on additional issues both in the textbook and in the methodological materials for teachers. Problem solving with the whole-part model has become more widespread after the analysis of the evaluation results conducted by PISA and TIMSS international evaluation organizations. Thus, PISA offers 15-year-old students in its evaluations with the motto "Learn to live" to solve tasks that include the mathematical model of real situations. This requires students to have the ability to correctly analyze the text of the tasks, take it seriously and draw conclusions. The training experience of countries that have shown high results is praised and disseminated, and new approaches are presented. One of these approaches is not to solve the problem by building an equation, but to solve it by calculation method. Thus, the student applies appropriate arithmetic by asking step-by-step questions according to the condition of the problem.

At the same time, drawing a full-part model according to the condition of the problem allows to imagine the situation with all its classification and to solve the problem easily. In the whole-part model, the student sees what each step of solving the problem describes in a real situation. When solving the problems, students explain how they found a part of the whole according to the information given in the problem and what action was performed at that time (how many equal parts the quantity was divided into), what information they found the divided part and what action was performed at that time. Students can find origami examples on the Internet, it is recommended to make such samples independently in their free time. These exercises are a very useful tool for developing the student's spatial imagination, installation and manual skills.

We can consider the study of mathematics in grades I-IV as the first step in the full mastery of school mathematics. The use of schematic tables has an important role in the development of creative activity of primary school students. This idea is extensively analyzed in the existing literature and articles, and recommendations are given on how the teacher should work on the condition of the issue with the students. It is clear that problem-solving techniques using diagrams and tables are mastered primarily as a result of solving a large number of problem types.

Solving problems related to the use of schemes and tables in primary classes leads to the development of both their creative and logical thinking. It creates favorable conditions for the application of developmental, problem-based learning methods through problem solving on the use of schemes and tables in primary classes. Problem-based learning is the sequential solution of problem situations, usually created for educational purposes.

Examples

Issue 1

A notebook is 2 times more expensive than a pencil and 3 times cheaper than a book. They gave 36 kopecks for the notebook, pencil and book together. How much are books, notebooks and pencils separately?

Let's show the short writing of the problem with a scheme.

We accept a conventional unit of length: we denote the price of a pencil by a piece. Then with that conventional unit, the notebook will be 2 units, and the book will be 6 units. In fact, we express the prices of notebooks and books by the price of a pencil: That is, for the money given for 1 notebook, you can buy 2 pencils. You can buy 6 pencils for the price of 1 book. So, you can buy 9 pencils for 36 cents. Then you can find the price of one pencil:

$$36:9= 4 \text{ chapters}$$

Issue 2

Find the sides of a rectangle with an area of 72 dm² and a perimeter of 34 dm.

Let's use the table:

A	B	6	4	3	2
B	9	12	18	24	36
P	34	36	44	54	76
S	72	72	72	72	72

Answer: If $a=8$ and $b=9$, the conditions of the problem are satisfied.

Issue 3

Elshad, Imran and Qadir are 25 years old together. It is known that Elshad is more than 5 years old and

younger than Imran. Imran is 3 years younger than Qadir. How old is everyone?

In solving this problem, it is necessary to use the sampling method.

<i>Elshad</i>	<i>Imran</i>	<i>Qadir</i>	<i>TOTAL</i>
6	7	10	23 – does not pay
7	8	11	26 - does not pay
6	8	11	25 – IT PAYS

So, the student should choose 3 numbers so that their total is 25. It is also known that

the age of two people cannot be expressed by a two-digit number separately. The age of all three cannot be a single digit number. Therefore, Qadir's age should be expressed only with a two-digit number.

Answer: Elshad is 6 years old

Imran 8 years old

Able 11 years

Issue 4

The total number of TV and computer parts sold in the store during the day was 56. The number of computer parts sold was 12 more than TV parts. How many computer parts were sold?

Complete: total number of items sold - 56

Parts: separate number of TV and computer parts.

$$56-12=44$$

$$44: 2= 22 \text{ (television detail)}$$

$$22+12=34 \text{ (computer detail)}$$

Issue 5

Tarla's money is 20 manat more than Asmar's. Theirs

together they have 60 manat money. How many manat money do Asmar and Tarla have separately?

Let's solve this problem with the whole-part model.

1) If we subtract Tarlan's excess money from the sum, $(60 - 20 = 40)$ each of them has the same with the amount of money, we will find how much money Tarlan and Asmar have together.

2) If we divide 40 manats into 2 parts, we can find out how many manats Asmar has:

$$40 : 2 = 20 \text{ (manat)}$$

3) If we subtract Asmar's money from the total, 60 manats, we get the amount of Tarla's money:

$$60 - 20 = 40 \text{ (manat)}$$

One can begin to develop the skills of finding a fraction of a number by researching problems related to finding a fraction.

Study 1. 12 counting tools, for example, beans (pencil, cube, straw, etc.) are distributed equally among 4 students. Students figure out that 12 beans each fall into a quarter. Teacher: How many beans did each of you get? 3 beans. Teacher: What fraction can be expressed for each of you? with a fraction of $\frac{1}{4}$. 12 beans are divided into 4 equal groups and each group (part) is assigned. 4 here is the denominator, that is, the number

That is, to find three-quarters of beans, one-fourth of it is first found: $12:4=3$. Then, the number indicating one part (3) is multiplied by the number of separated parts, that is, the number in the copy (3). $3*3=9$ (beans)

It is recommended to solve problems related to fractions not by applying the rule of finding the part of a number, but by drawing a whole-part model. The model allows the student to visually see the size, number, and whole of equal parts.

When solving the problems, the students explain how they found a part of the whole according to the information given in the problem and what action was performed at that time (how many equal parts the quantity was divided into), according to what information they found the divided part and what action was performed at that time.

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of equal parts, and the numerator shows 1 part given to each student. So $\frac{1}{4}$ of 12 beans is 3 beans.

Investigations on the issue are ongoing. One of the students gives his beans to the student named A. Question: Can we now guess that the beans are divided into 4 parts and each student gets equal parts? Students' opinions are listened to. Again, we can say that the beans are divided into 4 parts, but in A. there are 2 parts of equal shares, that is, there are $\frac{2}{4}$ parts. How many beans is that? A. counts his beans and it turns out that there are 6 beans. That is, $\frac{2}{4}$ of 12 beans is 6 beans. Then another student also gives his part to A. Now $\frac{3}{4}$ of all the beans are in A. and his number of beans is 9. Discussions are summarized on the fractional model. To find a fraction by number: 1) First a fraction is found. 2) The number of allocated parts (the number in the copy) is multiplied by the number corresponding to one part.

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